

MAIN APPROACHES AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY.

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Annotation: This comprehensive article delves into the multifaceted approaches and techniques employed in teaching English vocabulary, catering to a diverse range of learners and learning styles. Beginning with direct vocabulary instruction, the article explores traditional methods such as word lists and flashcards, providing a solid foundation for language learners. It then delves into contemporary strategies, including contextual learning, multimedia integration, and the incorporation of technology to enhance vocabulary acquisition in real-life contexts.

Word families and morphology are discussed as effective tools for deciphering unfamiliar words, emphasizing the importance of understanding the roots and origins of vocabulary. Semantic mapping is highlighted as a visual and organizational technique that fosters a deeper comprehension of word relationships. The inclusion of vocabulary journals and personalized notebooks empowers learners to take ownership of their language development, promoting self-directed learning.

The article recognizes the role of play and engagement in language acquisition, introducing word games, puzzles, and interactive activities as dynamic tools to make learning enjoyable. Repetition and spaced learning are acknowledged as powerful strategies for reinforcing vocabulary over time, maximizing retention. In essence, this article serves as a valuable resource for educators and learners alike, offering a nuanced exploration of diverse methods to enrich and expand English vocabulary. By presenting a blend of traditional and modern approaches, the article encourages a flexible and adaptive teaching environment, fostering a more comprehensive and effective language learning experience.

Key Words: *English Vocabulary Instruction, Teaching Techniques, Vocabulary Acquisition, Language Learning Strategies, Direct Instruction, Contextual Learning, Multimedia in Education, Morphology and Word Families, Semantic Mapping*

“Vocabulary acquisition is the largest and most important task facing the language learner.” (Swan and Walter 1984)

MODERN TECHNIQUES IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. In modern methodology two main tendencies set apart: methods in which the teacher has the most important role and chooses the items students will learn opposing the

one where focus shifts away from the teacher to the students. This makes students more responsible for their own learning and allows to meet individual needs of each student.

Grammar-translation vs. communicative approach. In recent years , there has been a major shift in perspective within the language teaching profession concerning the nature of what is to be taught. In simple terms, there has been a change of emphasis from presenting language as a set of forms (grammatical , phonological, lexical) which have to be learned and practised, to presenting language as a functional system which is used to fulfil a range of communicative purposes, which is described as communicative competence. The aim of this thesis is to present both attitudes, which are still widely used in foreign language education area. Each method is introduced concerning its principles and the advantageous place for practical application is elicited.

Grammar-translation method. The grammar-translation method of foreign language teaching is one of the most traditional methods, dating back to the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. It was originally used to teach 'dead' languages (and literatures) such as Latin and Greek. However, conscious learning of grammar is no longer the leading strategy in language educating area. The principal characteristic of the grammar-translation method is a focus on learning the grammar rules and their application in translating texts from one language into the other. Most of the teaching is provided in students' first language. Vocabulary is presented mainly through direct translation from the native language and memorization, using bilingual word list.

The basic unit of a teaching process is a sentence. Students spend most of the lesson time completing grammar exercises, where the main emphasis is laid on accuracy and following given structure. The grammar is presented systematically, in students native language and practiced through translation from one language to the other. e.g. Do you have my book? = Máš moji knihu?

They plan their utterance while their conversational partner is talking. Their output may be accurate, but they all too often do not pay enough attention to what the other person is saying. Students often have difficulties "relating" to the language, because the classroom experience keeps them from personalizing it or developing their own style. Grammar-translation method should be tempered with other approaches to create a more flexible and conducive methodology. The list of linguistics attitudes to grammar translation method could be finished by Barnhouse, 1981: "In English teaching dominated by the grammartranslation method, accuracy is emphasized more than fluency. Students in such classrooms

are extremely particular about linguistic details. They never feel satisfied with their language productions until the correct answers are provided. They are keenly interested in the exact words, have a low tolerance of ambiguity, and tend to focus on discrete grammar points and specific syntactic constructions.”

Considering the aim of this thesis we must admit a great deal of grammar translation method for generations of people educated in such a way. It would not be fair to condemn it for being old-fashioned and worthless. On the other side, it would be of no value to insist on out-dated methods. As shown in the experiment later, the progress in language teaching method can significantly influence students’ motivation as well as their linguistic and communicative competence.

The role of grammar Despite all of the drawbacks mentioned above, there are several positive aspects to be found in this approach. The supporter of grammar translation method, Rao Zhenhui, emphasizes the importance of the language structure as a fundamental element which allows us to generate sentences. Only correct grammar structure can assure comprehensible communication. Conscious utilizing of grammar rules improve students grammatical accuracy, nevertheless this should not interfere with communication. For that it is essential to take into account the time necessary for new structure acquisition. In classroom conditions it is advantageous to apply this approach for activities such as writing and prepared speech, when students must be thinking about correctness or focus on form. Within these terms, given a reasonable time students are able to use obtained skills to great benefit.

The role of translation “Translation seems to be a useful tool if used sparingly, but it should be used with caution.” If teachers rely on the use of translation to excess , students are losing some of the essential spirit of being in a language learning classroom. This often cause listening skills decline. Furthermore, Harmer points to the difficulties of translation, which requires an efficient speaker of both languages to translate well. “Sometimes it is worth giving the mother tongue equivalent rather than to pending valuable time trying to define or show the meaning. It is of great value when no easy alternative suggests itself or highlight the danger of false cognates.”

Communicative approach. The communicative approach is an umbrella term to describe the methodology which teaches students how to communicate efficiently . It also lays emphasis on students responsibility for their own learning. It involves cooperation within group, self-activity, dictionary work. The first concern of communicative approach is language acquisition rather than

conscious learning. According to Krashen, “ acquisition is a natural process, similar to the way children develop ability in their first language. It is subconscious process when students are not aware of the fact they are acquiring language but are using the language for communication.”

Communicative approach refers to classroom activities in which students use language as a vehicle of communication, and the main purpose is to complete some kind of task. Students are required to use any and/or all the language that they know, and they gradually develop their strategies in communication. There is a place for both controlled presentation and semicontrolled language practice, which brings optimal development of students’ language skills.

Teaching Vocabulary. Principles of learning and teaching vocabulary However many theories about vocabulary learning process were written , it still remains the matter of memory. Thus, there are several general principles for successful teaching , which are valid for any method. According to Wallace, 1988 the principles are:

- aim
- what is to be taught, which words, how many
- need
- target vocabulary should respond students’ real needs and interests
- frequent exposure and repetition
- meaningful presentation
- clear and unambiguous denotation or reference should be assured.

Learning vocabulary is a complex process. The students’ aim to be reached in learning vocabulary process is primarily their ability to recall the word at will and to recognize it in its spoken and written form. Generally, knowing a word involves knowing its form and its meaning at the basic level. In deeper aspects it means the abilities to know its:

- 1) Meaning, i.e. relate the word to an appropriate object or context
- 2) Usage, i.e. knowledge of its collocations, metaphors and idioms, as well as style and register (the appropriate level of formality), to be aware of any connotations and associations the word might have
- 3) Word formation, i.e. ability to spell and pronounce the word correctly, to know any derivations (acceptable prefixes and suffixes),
- 4) Grammar, i.e. to use it in the appropriate grammatical form.

How words are remembered Unlike the learning of grammar, which is essentially a rule based system, vocabulary knowledge is largely a question of accumulating individual items. The general rule seems to be a question of

memory. And during the process of teaching and learning vocabulary an important problem occurs: How does memory work? Researchers into the workings of memory distinguish between the following systems

- short- term store
- working memory
- long- term memory

Short - term store. Short-term store is the brain capacity to hold a limited number of items of information for periods of time up to a few seconds. It is the kind of memory that is involved in repeating a word that you have just heard the teacher modelling. But successful vocabulary learning involves more than holding words for a few seconds. To integrate words into long - term memory they need to be subjected to different kinds of operations. Working memory Working memory means focussing on word long enough to perform operations on them. It means the information is manipulated via the senses from external sources and/or can be downloaded from the long- term memory. Material remains in working memory for about twenty seconds. The existence of articulator loop enables this new material processing. It works a bit like audiotape going round a round again. It assures the short- term store to be kept refreshed. The ability to hold a word in working memory is a good predictor of language learning aptitude. The better ability to hold words in working memory the smoother the process of learning foreign languages is.

Long -term memory. Long-term memory can be seen as kind of filling system. Unlike working memory, which has a limited capacity and no permanent content, this kind of memory has an enormous capacity and its contents are durable over time. However, to ensure moving new materials into permanent long-term memory, requires number of principles to be followed, described by Thornbury, 2002:

- Repetition - repetition of encounters with a word is very important, useful and effective. If the word is met several times over space interval during reading activities, students have a very good chance to remember it for a long time.
- Retrieval - another kind of repetition. Activities, which require retrieval, such as using the new items in written tasks, help students to be able to recall it again in the future.
- Spacing - it is useful to split memory work over a period of time rather than to mass it together in a single block.
- Pacing - to respect different learning styles and pace, students should be ideally given the opportunity to do memory work individually.

- Use - putting words to use, preferably in an interesting way, is the best way of ensuring they are added to long – term memory. This is so called “Use it or lose it” principle.
- Cognitive depth - the more decisions students make about the word and the more cognitively demanding these decisions are, the better the word is remembered.
- Personal organising - personalisation significantly increased the probability that students will remember new items. It is achieved mainly through conversation and role-playing activities.
 - Imaging – easily visualised words are better memorable than those that do not evoke with any pictures. Even abstract words can be associated with some mental image.
- Mnemonics – tricks to help retrieve items or rules that are stored in memory. The best kinds of mnemonics are visuals and keyword techniques.
 - Motivation - strong motivation itself does not ensure that words will be remembered. Even unmotivated students remember words if they have to face appropriate tasks.
 - Attention - it is not possible to improve vocabulary without a certain degree of conscious attention.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this article serves as a comprehensive guide for educators and learners seeking to enhance English vocabulary proficiency. By embracing a combination of traditional and modern approaches, individuals can tailor their learning experience to match their unique preferences and needs. From direct instruction to playful word games and the integration of multimedia, these strategies create a rich and dynamic environment for effective vocabulary acquisition. Understanding the nuances of each approach empowers educators to design engaging lessons and supports learners in developing a robust and versatile vocabulary skill set. Teaching vocabulary is a dynamic and nuanced process that requires a combination of strategic principles, thoughtful considerations, and best practices. By integrating relevance, multisensory approaches, and differentiation, educators can create an inclusive and engaging learning environment. Ongoing assessment, collaboration, and technology integration further enhance the effectiveness of vocabulary instruction, fostering a rich and meaningful language learning experience for students.

References:

1. Breen, J., and D. Candlin. 1980. The essentials of a communicative curriculum in language teaching. *Applied Linguistics*, 1, 2, pp. 89–112

2. Collins English Dictionary for Advanced learners, third edition, 2001
Gairns, Ruth, Redman, Stuart: Working with Words, A guide to teaching and learning vocabulary, Cambridge University Press, 1986
3. Harmer, Jeremy: The Practise of English Language teaching, Longman, 1993
4. Howatt A.P.R. (1984) A History of English Language Teaching (OUP)
Hymes, D. H. 1981. On communicative competence. In The communicative approach to language teaching. (ed.) C. J.
5. Brumfit and K. Johnson. Oxford: Oxford University Press
Krashen, Stephen: Principles and Practice in second language acquisition Logman, 1993
6. Nunan David: Language Teaching Methodology, a textbook for teachers
Longman ,2000 Oxenden Clive, Seligson Paul, Latham Coenig Christina: English File 2, Oxford University Press, 1997
7. Peprník J., Nangonová S., Zábajová E.: Angličtina pro jazykové školy 1, Státní pedagogické nakladatelství Praha, 1981
8. Rossner, Richard- Bolitho, Rod: Currents of Change in English Language Teaching, Oxford University Press, 1990